

Project Charter

PROJECT OVERVIEW

PROJECT NAME	Citing Marx: <i>Die Neue Zeit</i> , 1891-1918		
PRIMARY INVESTIGATOR	Edward Baring	GRANT	CDH Research Partnership
EXPECTED START DATE	Feb 10, 2025	EXPECTED END DATE	Aug 11, 2025

PROJECT DETAILS

PROJECT ABSTRACT

“Citing Marx” aims to track published citations of the *Manifest der Kommunistischen Partei* and *Das Kapital* (vol. 1) within articles of *Die Neue Zeit*, a socialist periodical, focusing on volumes published between 1891 and 1918. Encompassing a period which saw some of the most important debates and developments within Marxism before the Russian Revolution, the data generated through this phase of “Citing Marx” will support an exploration of whether and how these events impacted the way socialist thinkers engaged with and used Marx’s writings through their changing patterns of citation.

One provisional hypothesis of the research team concerns the impact of the “Revisionism Controversy,” a debate starting around 1897 that is often taken to foreshadow the break between socialism and communism. We expect that the beginning of “Revisionism Controversy” will coincide with a changing pattern of citation in *Die Neue Zeit*, and we expect to discover different citation strategies for the two sides – orthodox and revisionist – in the post-partnership analysis of the data.

PURPOSE/AUDIENCE

This research partnership aims to produce a reusable software pipeline that can accurately detect citations (direct attributed quotes and named references) of the *Manifest der Kommunistischen Partei* and *Das Kapital* within *Die Neue Zeit*.

The pipeline will be developed with an eye toward extensibility for other journals, other languages, and other texts written by Marx. Initially, the software will be of use to the project team, but we think that scholars working on the Marxist tradition will find both the software-pipeline and the generated data valuable, even though the project’s results will be based upon a subset of *Die Neue Zeit* publications. The research team hopes to organize an international workshop in 2026, to share the software and resulting data, and discuss possibilities for further development.

<p>DELIVERABLES (IN ORDER OF PRIORITY)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A reusable and extensible software pipeline that detects citations of Marx in <i>Die Neue Zeit</i>, 1891-1918 (interface TBD: possibilities include notebook or command-line interface) • A published (with DOI) dataset of citations to <i>Manifest der Kommunistischen Partei</i> and <i>Das Kapital</i> (vol. 1) found in <i>Die Neue Zeit</i>, 1891-1918, deposited either on Zenodo or PUL's Data Commons • A white paper published on Zenodo that serves as the public record of the project, documenting the goals, participants, outcomes, evaluation, and anticipated next steps • Included in the dataset, citations of 5-6 additional texts written by Marx, found in <i>Die Neue Zeit</i>, 1891-1918. Chosen texts will depend on availability from MEGAdigital • Included in the dataset, citations to <i>Manifest der Kommunistischen Partei</i> and <i>Das Kapital</i> (vol. 1) found in other German-language journals, such as <i>Sozialistische Monatshefte</i> • Extension of the software to include detecting allusions, indirect quotes/paraphrases, and Marxist lingua franca phrases 	<p>Code ▾</p> <p>Dataset ▾</p> <p>Writing (articl... ▾</p> <p>Dataset ▾</p> <p>Dataset ▾</p> <p>Code ▾</p>	<p>Must-Have ▾</p> <p>Must-Have ▾</p> <p>Must-Have ▾</p> <p>Could-Have ▾</p> <p>Could-Have ▾</p> <p>Wish-To-H... ▾</p>
<p>OUT OF SCOPE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detecting citations in <i>Die Neue Zeit</i> issues prior to 1891 or after 1918 • Creating a database • Cross-lingual citation detection • Publicly accessible, hosted interface or website for use by non-team members • Digital scholarly edition of Marx's texts with "heat map" of citations • Custom data analysis and data visualization of the citations 		
<p>SUCCESS CRITERIA</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software pipeline finds at least 90% of citations to <i>Manifest der Kommunistischen Partei</i> and <i>Das Kapital</i> (vol. 1) in <i>Die Neue Zeit</i> between 1891 		

- and 1918
- PI can use the software pipeline & manage which texts are used as input independently
- Software pipeline is verified content agnostic (i.e., can be used with other German-language texts written by Marx, additional volumes of *Die Neue Zeit*, and/or other German-language journals)

SUSTAINABILITY PLAN
 During project closeout, the CDH will provide the PI with a Short-Term Service Agreement (STSA). Whenever possible, existing and open-source software will be used over custom solutions to minimize maintenance required in the post-partnership phase (e.g. for filtering, sorting, and visualizing dataset).

POST-PARTNERSHIP ACTIVITIES
 The research team plans to use the data generated during the partnership to co-write a scholarly article. The research team also plans to organize a workshop/colloquium for scholars to explore the dataset using existing filtering tools.
 The RSE team plans to write a technical paper on the experimentation and methods for submission to a computational humanities venue, such as the CHR conference or CHR journal.

PROJECT PHASES WITH MILESTONE OUTCOMES

Phase	Milestone Outcome	Anticipated Time
Annotation	Set of hand-curated annotations of citations in <i>Die Neue Zeit</i> (currently 1896-1906 are OCR'd & 1896-1901 are annotated)	Pre-partnership
Experimentation / Technical Requirements Planning	Notes and notebooks (where appropriate) demonstrating and evaluating a few different methods of citation detection, such as a notebook using NER with spaCy A recommendation on the best approach and tool format Results in the technical specifications document outlining the major contours of the software to be developed	3 months
Completing corpus of machine-readable text	OCR of <i>Die Neue Zeit</i> issues 1891-1895 and 1907-1918	2 weeks (in tandem with experimentation)
Software	1.0 release of software/pipeline. Includes evaluation, testing,	3 months

development	and iterating toward shipping working software that meets success criteria.	
Project Closeout	Submit dataset for review by PRDS and publish dataset on chosen platform. Write up white paper. Issue STSA, off-boarding from CDH platforms, documentation and training on software use.	Post-partnership

DEPENDENCIES & RISKS

DEPENDENCIES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Current annotation method is dependent on Recogito For HPC use, PI will need to submit an application to access to Della
POTENTIAL RISKS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Because Recogito occasionally goes down, the PM will periodically download data and upload to Google Drive to mitigate data loss. If the initial set of annotations is insufficient for evaluating/training, PI and PM may need to complete additional annotations. If Princeton's free eScriptorium instance is not available to OCR the remaining issues of <i>Die Neue Zeit</i>, PI will need to secure funding for commercial solution (e.g. Transkribus).
RIGHTS + PERMISSIONS	We have permission from the Friedrich Ebert Library and the Berlin-Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften to use both the <i>Neue Zeit</i> texts and the Marx texts. We would need to engage in further negotiations with the various rights holders if we decided that we also wanted to give access to the original sources.

PROJECT TEAM

Name	Role on Project	Dept	Role Description
Edward G. Bari...	Principal Investigator	HIS -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responsible for overall project direction and for providing regular feedback/software testing to RSE team during meetings and asynchronously.
Bennett Nagte...	Project Manager	HIS -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responsible for coordinating the communication and work of the project team, including facilitating team meetings, maintaining project documentation, and

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> managing task-tracking in Asana. May assist with data work/feature testing.
Rebecca Koeser	Co-PI, Technical Lead	CDH ▾	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accountable and responsible for the technical direction, design, and execution of the project.
Laure Thomps...	Research Software Engineer	CDH ▾	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responsible for the technical direction, design, and execution of the project.
Mary Naydan	Technical PM	CDH ▾	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responsible for defining, scoping, and prioritizing the work for the RSE team.
Jeri Wieringa	Project Advisor	CDH ▾	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responsible for advising on the design and direction of the project and for coordinating with the larger CDH portfolio.

BUDGET

[Project budget available on request.]

TERMS OF COLLABORATION

DOCUMENTATION + COMMUNICATION

Slack will be used for most day-to-day communication among team members. Meeting notes, data, and documentation will be stored in a shared folder within the CDH Research Partnership shared **Google Drive**. **Asana** will be used for non-development-related task management; all team members are expected to check off tasks promptly to asynchronously communicate on progress. A public **GitHub** repository under the Princeton-CDH organization will be used for managing development-related tasks (issues), code, and code documentation. A separate, additional GitHub repository (modeled on [PGP's](#)) will be used to version and publish data, view it via Flat GitHub, allow download of the CSV data, and serve as the basis for the dataset publication. For the duration of the research partnership, the project team is expected to meet at least once every other week to discuss progress and make decisions. Meeting frequency may need to be adjusted once active development ramps up to meet team needs. In the case of a breakdown in communication, the CDH Assistant Director may intervene to help find a mutually agreeable solution or, in very rare cases, negotiate the end of the partnership.

CREDIT + ATTRIBUTION

The project team recognizes the collaborative nature of the digital humanities and, in contrast to the single-authorship model of the traditional humanities, embraces an inclusive practice of authorship. Following the recommendation of Princeton Research Computing's [RSE Partnership Guide](#), if a publication would not have been

	<p>possible without RSE project team members, then the RSEs should be included as co-authors. All student labor related to the partnership, unless part of a student’s coursework, must be fairly compensated, and we encourage at minimum citation, or co-authorship if appropriate, of students and data workers in all related publications, including datasets, articles, and monographs.</p>
PUBLICITY	<p>The CDH Communications Manager may publicize the project and related information (such as images, links, and text) on the CDH website and newsletter, in annual reports, and on select social media (e.g. Bluesky, LinkedIn). In some cases, the Communications Manager may also work with Princeton’s Office of Communications to publicize the project on Princeton media sources such as its website, social media, newsletters, magazines. To produce effective and quality publicity of the project, the Communications Manager may request additional media and information from the PI.</p>
EXTENSIONS	<p>The PI may request an extension beyond the allotted partnership timeframe to complete the agreed-upon deliverables by submitting a written rationale to the CDH Assistant Director, cc’ing the CDH Project Manager. Extensions may also be proposed and automatically granted by the CDH Assistant Director due to delays in the CDH development schedule.</p>
AMENDMENTS	<p>Amendments to the charter should be requested in writing to all project team members and the CDH Assistant Director. Changes will be recorded in the “Version History” section below. Please also update the date in the charter header.</p>

SIGNATORIES

PREPARED BY	Mary Naydan Bennett Nagtegaal Rebecca Koeser Edward Baring	Jan 13, 2025
REVIEWED BY	Jeri Wieringa Rebecca Koeser Edward Baring Natalia Ermolaev Bennett Nagtegaal Laure Thompson Mary Naydan	Feb 4, 2025 Feb 4, 2025 Feb 4, 2025 Feb 4, 2025 Feb 5, 2025 Feb 5, 2025 Feb 6, 2025
APPROVED BY	Meredith Martin	Feb 10, 2025

RECOMMENDED CITATION

Naydan, Mary, Bennett Nagtegaal, Rebecca Sutton Koeser, and Edward Baring. *CDH Project Charter – Citing Marx 2025*. Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton. 2025.
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14861082>.